

Investigation into Black Oxide Coating of 410 Grade Surgical Stainless Steel Using Alkaline Bath Treatment

K. K. Saju, A. R. Reghuraj

Abstract—High reflectance of surgical instruments under bright light hinders the visual clarity during laparoscopic surgical procedures leading to loss of precision and device control and creates strain and undesired difficulties to surgeons. Majority of the surgical instruments are made of surgical grade steel. Instruments with a non reflective surface can enhance the visual clarity during precision surgeries. A conversion coating of black oxide has been successfully developed 410 grade surgical stainless steel. The characteristics of the developed coating suggests the application of this technique for developing 410 grade surgical instruments with minimal reflectance.

Keywords—Conversion coatings, 410 stainless steel, black oxide, reflectance.

I. INTRODUCTION

STAINLESS steels are widely used for the manufacture of surgical instruments [1]. Reflection under bright lights from the surgical instruments made of surgical grade stainless steel creates undesired difficulties to the surgeons like loss of precision, lack of device control etc in laparoscopic surgeries [2]. The precision and device control in laparoscopic and key-hole surgeries are vital. Matte black oxide coating of surgical steels have been suggested to reduce the problems created due to the reflection of light from the surgical instruments made of surgical grade stainless steel. Black oxide is a conversion coating formed on the metal surfaces as a result of chemical reaction of the metal atoms with an oxidizing agent like air, alkaline aqueous salt solution, and molten salts. The conversion coating is a film of chemical compound formed by the reaction of the substrate in air and the properties do not vary from the main substrate [3].

Black oxide coating provides reduced light glare, dimensional stability, anti-galling property, improved lubricity, superior finish, corrosion protection etc [4]. The various black oxide processes are hot alkaline black oxide process, cold black oxide process, and molten salt black oxide process [7]. These methods have been tried for coating 300 series grade surgical stainless steel. Currently surgical equipments are manufactured from superior grade 410 stainless steels. The martensitic stainless steel is strong, hard, has good wear resistance but less resistance to corrosion [5]. In the present study all three methods suggested for conversion coating of 300 series stainless steel has been investigated on 410 grade steel by altering the various parameters like the composition of the mixture, time and

temperature. It was found that a black oxide (Ferric oxide, Fe_3O_4) conversion coating with good characteristics can be developed on grade 410 stainless steel using the molten salt process with a composition of 400g/L of sodium hydroxide, 320g/L sodium nitrate, and 200g/L of sodium dichromate in water at a temperature of 1390C and coating duration of 40 minutes. The reflectance, thickness and surface roughness parameters of the coating suggest its application for black oxide coating of surgical instruments made of 410 grade stainless steel so as to obtain minimal reflecting surgical surfaces.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

A. Materials and Sample Preparation

Type SAE grade 410, 316L & 310, stainless steel mechanically cleaned, degreased in alkaline solution followed by a pickling process in 20% diluted Hydrochloric acid were used as the specimens [6]. Prepared samples are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Prepared samples ready for coating process

B. Deposition Procedure

Coating of black oxide was attempted by three methods as detailed below. For each method the coating solution was transferred to a heating container of 50 litres capacity with two heating coils with heating capacity up to 3000C. The solution was allowed to reach the required coating temperature for each method. Then the specimens were partially dipped in the high temperature solution so as to get the required coating. The specimens were taken out at intervals of 5, 15, 25, 35, 45 and 55 minutes monitored by a calibrated stopwatch.

Method 1: By treating in hot solution of sodium hydroxide, sodium nitrate and sodium nitrite in water with a composition of 700g/L of sodium hydroxide, 100g/L of sodium nitrate and 100g/L of sodium nitrite in water. A 10 litre of solution was used to completely immerse the heating coils in the heater vessel used. After weighing in the chemicals and mixing them in water, the

K.K.Saju is with the Department of Mechanical Engineering, School of Engineering, Cochin University of Science and Technology, Kochi Kerala India (phone: 91-484-2577688, 91-9895593988, fax 91-484-2577688, e-mail kksaju1970@gmail.com).

mixture was transferred to the heating container. The mixture was maintained at a temperature of 1400C during the coating process. [7]

Method 2: Coating by treating in solution having composition of 110g/L of potassium hydroxide, 200g/L of potassium nitrate in 10 litres of water. The mixture was maintained at a temperature of 1350C during the coating process. [7]

Method 3: Using composition of 400g/L of sodium hydroxide, 320g/L sodium nitrate, and 165g/L of sodium dichromate in 10 litres of water. The mixture was heated to a temperature of 1450C during the coating process. Fig. 2 shows the actual coating process in progress.[7]

Fig. 2 Setup showing the coating process

As the preliminary samples of 410 grade on physical verification showed uniform coating only by the method 3 and that too at longer intervals, this method was chosen for further investigation to get optimal time and temperature and composition for uniform black oxide coating of 410 grade stainless steel. This was done by subjecting 410 grade samples to coating by method 3 at temperatures varying between 1150C-1500C. The process was also further explored with varying percentage of the sodium dichromate ($\text{Na}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$) (50-350g/L) while maintaining the same composition for sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and sodium nitrate (NaNO_3).

C. Surface Characterization

Measurement of reflectance : Reflectivity is a vital parameter in this work. In optics and photometry, reflectivity is the fraction of incident radiation reflected by a surface. In general it must be treated as directional property that is the function of the reflected direction, incident direction, and the incident wavelength. However it is also commonly averaged over the reflected hemisphere to give the hemispherical spectral reflectivity. When reflection occurs from thin layers of material, internal reflection effects can cause the reflectance to vary with surface thickness. Reflectance is the fraction of electromagnetic power reflected from a specific sample, while reflectivity is a property of the material itself, which could be measured on a perfect machine if the material filled half of the space [8]. The reflectance of the samples were measured with UV-VIS-NIR spectrophotometer Varian, Cary 5000 with

Spectral range: 175 – 3300 nm Wave length accuracy: ± 0.1 nm (UV –Vis), ± 0.4 nm (NIR) Wave length reproducibility: 0.025 nm Limiting resolution: 0.05 nm (UV –Vis), 0.2 nm (NIR)

Measurement of thickness and roughness : Average thickness of the films and average roughness was measured using a Dektak 6M stylus profilometer (Veeco, USA) [9]-[11]. The stylus profiler takes measurements electromechanically by moving the sample beneath a diamond-tipped stylus. The film undergoing measurement is deposited with a region masked; this creates a step on the sample surface, and the thickness of the sample can be measured accurately by measuring the vertical motion of the stylus over the step. The profilometer measures the average thickness and roughness of the sample.

III.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the coating produced by the three methods on SAE grade steel samples of 310, 316 L and 410 are tabulated in Table I. On preliminary observation it was found that a good uniform dull matte black coating was formed on the grade 410 steel specimens coated by method 3 at a coating time of 45 minutes. No coating was observed on the 316 L samples. As the base interest was to coat surgical steel of 410 grade, method 3 was taken up for further investigation with changes in coating parameters. Fig. 3 shows the samples after the coating procedure. Samples in Fig. 3(c) clearly show black oxide conversion coating.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 3 Photographs of 410 grade samples after the primary coating (a) Method 1 (b) Method 2; and (c) Method 3

The coating characteristics obtained by varying the temperature of the bath under method 3 without altering the composition of the solution and time of coating are tabulated in Table II. A thin layer of conversion coating was observed on the specimen for all temperatures from 1200C to 1450C. The coating formed at a temperature of 1300C returned the lowest reflectance along with the maximum thickness and minimum roughness. Fig. 4 shows the variation of thickness, roughness and percentage reflectance of the samples for the various temperatures. Fig. 5 shows the variation in sample colour in different samples from black to brown.

TABLE I
 TABULATED RESULTS OF BLACK OXIDE COATING ON VARIOUS GRADE OF STEEL BY THE THREE METHODS

Sl no	Chemical composition	Steel Grade	Coating Time	coating	Colour	Visual examination	Results
	Chemical quantity						
Method 1 (max temp 140 ^o C)							
1.	Sodium Hydroxide	0.700 kg	5	No	-		
			15	No	-		
	Sodium Nitrate	0.100 kg	SAE 410	35	No	-	No coating was observed
			SAE 310	45	No	-	
			SAE316L	45	Uniform	Black	Fine uniform coating
water	1 litre	SAE316L	45	No	-	No coating observed	
Method 2 (max temp 135 ^o C)							
2.	Potassium Hydroxide	1.100 kg	5	No	-		
			15	No	-		
	Potassium Nitrate	0.200 kg	SAE 410	35	No	-	No coating observed
			SAE 310	45	No	-	
			SAE316L	45	Uniform	Black	Fine uniform coating
water	1 litre	SAE316L	45	No	-	No coating observed	
Method 3 (max temp 140 ^o C)							
3.	Sodium Hydroxide	0.400 kg	5	Traces	Black		
			15	Traces	Black	Black coating was observed which became more uniform with increase in coating time	
	Sodium Nitrate	0.320 kg	SAE 410	35	Non uniform	Black	
			SAE 310	45	Uniform	Black	
			SAE316L	45	Uniform	Black	Uniform coating
water	1 litre	SAE316L	45			No coating observed	

Fig. 4 Variance of Reflectance, thickness, and roughness at different temperatures

TABLE II
TABULATED RESULTS OF BLACK OXIDE COATING ON 410 GRADE SAMPLES FOR THE VARIOUS TEMPERATURES

Exp no	Temperature	Specimen	Time of exposure	Coating	Colour	% R	t	Ra
1	115 ^o C	1	45	None	--	23.93	3.11	0.204
3	120 ^o C	2	45	Traces	Black	20.96	3.69	0.157
3	125 ^o C	3	45	Non uniform	Black	17.67	4.54	0.178
4	130 ^o C	4	45	Uniform	Black	14.67	4.58	0.157
5	135 ^o C	5	45	Uniform	Brown black	15.68	4.62	0.168
6	140 ^o C	6	45	Uniform	Brown	18.18	4.28	0.211
7	145 ^o C	7	45	Uniform	Brown	23.08	4.82	0.196

*t- thickness of coating obtained μm ; %R- average percentage of reflectance obtained in the visible region (380-750 nm); Ra- average roughness values in μm

Fig. 5 Colour variation of the coated samples

As austenitic steels have a higher reflectance than the ferritic and martensitic steels and their integrated solar reflectance of 68% is considered too much for their use in endoscopy two of the natural oxides on stainless steel, Fe₂O₃

and Cr₂O₃ have been studied as separate films, and their optical constants determined by combined transmission and reflectance measurements. It has been found that Fe₃O₄ and Cr₂O₃ gives better selectivity than Fe₂O₃. Hence it is concluded that the ferritic and martensitic steel base is to be preferred for developing surgical instrument because of its lower reflectance [12]. Based on this the surface conversion of SAE 410 grade steel was further investigated with dichromate leading to a surface layer of Fe₂O₄ and Cr₂O₃ which will have lower reflectivity.

TABLE III
TABULATED RESULTS OF BLACK OXIDE COATING ON 410 GRADE SAMPLE BY VARYING SODIUM DICHROMATE COMPOSITION

Exp No	Composition in kg/L (Na ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇)	Sample	Time of coating	Boiling point	Coating	Colour	%R	t	Ra
1	0.050	8	30	125 ^o C	Traces	-	23.08	1.02	0.128
		9	40			Black	18.95	1.93	0.168
		10	30			Black	17.33	1.96	0.179
3	0.100	11	40	133 ^o C	Non Uniform	Black	18.51	1.91	0.210
		12	30			Black	17.06	2.21	0.236
3	0.150	13	40	137 ^o C	Uniform	Black	15.68	3.16	0.162
		14	30			Black	15.73	4.69	0.140
4	0.200	15	40	139 ^o C	Uniform	Black	13.45	4.83	0.152
		16	30			Black	15.29	4.47	0.195
5	0.250	17	40	144 ^o C	Uniform	Brown	17.67	4.54	0.178
		18	30			Brown	19.73	4.13	0.152
6	0.300	19	40	150 ^o C	Uniform	Brown	21.16	3.39	0.139
		20	30			Brown	23.76	5.83	0.137
7	0.350	21	40	153 ^o C	Uniform	Brown	23.93	4.91	0.204

* t- thickness of coating obtained μm ; %R- average of percentage reflectance obtained in visible region (380-750nm); Ra- average roughness values in μm

Fig. 6 Variation of % of reflectance, thickness and roughness with change in sodium dichromate composition

Since di-chromate composition is detrimental in a lower reflective coating the 410 grade samples were subjected to coating process by method 3 by varying the dichromate composition and the results are tabulated in Table III. Fig. 6 shows the variation of thickness, roughness and percentage reflectance of the samples by varying the dichromate composition. It is seen that the coating done using composition of 400 g/L of sodium hydroxide, 320 g/L sodium nitrate, and 200 g/L of sodium dichromate in 10 litres of water with a coating temperature of 1390C and coating duration of 40 minutes gave a uniform black coating with the lowest reflectance of 13.45%, thickness of 4.83 μm and a low roughness of 0.152 μm and is shown in Fig. 7 (a). The other samples in figure show lesser coating characteristics.

Fig. 7 Coated samples by varying sodium dichromate composition

IV. CONCLUSION

Conversion Black oxide coating was successfully done on grade 410 stainless steel using hot alkaline process with alkaline solution consisting of sodium nitrate, sodium hydroxide and sodium dichromate. Analysis of the coated surfaces were further made based on temperature changes, time of coating, change in composition of solution and sodium di-chromate ratio to get the coating with maximum thickness and lowest reflectance and having average roughness at the lower range. The best coating was obtained with a solution of 400 g/L of sodium hydroxide, 320g/L of sodium nitrate, 200g/L of sodium Di-chromate in water at an alkaline bath temperature of 1390C and an exposure time of 40 minutes. The minimum average percentage of reflectance in visible region obtained was 13.45% and the thickness of the coating was 4.83 μm . The average roughness value is 0.152 μm . The reflectance value obtained is far less compared to base 410 grade Stainless steel samples and suggests the usage of the coating procedure for producing low reflective surgical instruments for laparoscopic and endoscopic application.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors wish to acknowledge the facilities extended for this work by Ms. Jayon Implants Palakkad, Kerala, India and wish to sincerely thank its proprietor Mr. Vijai for the same.

REFERENCES

[1] Gerald McDonnell, Denise Sheard -A Practical Guide to Decontamination in Healthcare. (2012), Wiley Blackwell Publishers, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, West Sussex, UK ISBN-10: 1444330136, (70-75).

[2] Howard L. Levine, M. Pais Clemente -Sinus Surgery: Endoscopic and Microscopic Approaches. (2004), Thieme Publisher, ISBN-10: 0865779724, (174-178).

[3] N. Arab & M. Rahimi Nezhad Soltani -A Study of Coating Process of Cast Iron Blackening. Journal of Applied Chemical Research, 9, 13-23 (2009) ISSN: 2008-3815.

[4] Mel Schwartz -Encyclopedia and Handbook of Materials, Parts and Finishes. Second Edition, (2002), CRC Press LLC, Florida, ISBN-10: 1566766613, 479-490.

[5] Mikell P. Groover- Fundamentals of Modern Manufacturing: Materials, Processes, and systems. Fourth edition, (2010), John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, ISBN-10: 0470467002, 114-116.

[6] Standard Recommended practice for cleaning and descaling stainless steel parts, equipment, and systems. Cleaning stainless steel, ASTM STP 538, American Society for Testing Materials, (1973), 1- 16.

[7] Linden H Wagner Corrosion resistance of black oxide coatings on mild and corrosion resistant steels, Engineering Support of Standardization Project X.O. 76502-0001,1964

[8] F. Khelifaoui, Y. Bellouard, T. Gessmann, X. Wang, Harvard University; J. Vlassak, M. Hafez -An Investigation of the Oxidation of Laser and Furnace-Annealed Sputter-Deposited NiTi Thin Films Using Reflectivity Measurements. SMST-2004, Proceedings of the International Conference on Shape Memory and Superelastic Technologies, ASM International (2006), 427-434.

[9] K.K. Saju, Sasidharan Vidyand, N.H. Jayadas, Jackson James, M.K. Jayaraj -Effect Of Surface Characteristics Of Anodized Ti-6Al-4V Implant Material On Osteoblast Attachment And Proliferation. J.Orthopaedics (2009);6(1)e5.

[10] M. Haidopoulos, S. Turgeon -Development of an optimized electrochemical process for subsequent coating of 316 stainless steel for stent applications. J Mater Sci:Mater Med (2006) 17, 647-657.

[11] Bharat Bhushan -Principles and Applications of Tribology. second edition,(2013) John Wiley & Sons Ltd, New York, ISBN: 978-1-119-94454-6, 131-135.

[12] Bjorn Karlsson and Carl G. Ribbing -Optical constants and spectral selectivity of stainless steel and its oxides. J. Appl. Phys. 53, Issue 9, 6340 (1982).